

Gene cloning, expression and purification of Perforin like Protein-1 from *Plasmodium vivax*

Dissertation by

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DECLARATION

I, Vinay Yadav, student of the school of Interdisciplinary and applied Life Sciences, Central University of Haryana, Mahendergarh, hereby declare and certify that my dissertation entitled “**Gene cloning, expression and purification of Perforin like Protein-1 from *Plasmodium vivax***”, submitted to the Department of Microbiology, Central University of Haryana, India in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Science in Microbiology is a record of original research work done by me and the dissertation has not been the basis for the award of any degree/diploma/associateship/fellowship or similar title of any candidate of any university. I have faithfully and accurately cited all my sources, including books, journals, handouts and unpublished manuscripts, as well as any other media, such as the internet, letters or significant personal communications.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the dissertation entitled “**Gene cloning, expression and purification of Perforin like Protein-1 from *Plasmodium vivax***”, submitted to the Central University of Haryana in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Masters of Science in June 2018 is a record of original research work done by **VINAY YADAV (Roll no. – 9011)** at ICMR- National Institute of Malaria Research under the guidance of Dr. Anup Anvikar, Scientist ‘F’. It is further certified that to the best of our knowledge the dissertation has not formed the basis for the award on any degree/diploma/associateship/fellowship or similar title of any other candidate of any university.

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Attendance Certificate

This is to certify that Vinay Yadav attended ICMR- National Institute of Malarial Research from January 2018 to 7 June 2018 for his dissertation work. His total attendance for this period is 89 days. He is sincere, regular student and completed work assigned to him. I wish him for bright future ahead.

Good Luck!

.....

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ABSTRACT

Malaria is deadly disease caused by different species of *Plasmodium*, spread by infected female mosquito Anopheles bite to healthy person. *Plasmodium falciparum* & *Plasmodium vivax* is equally prevalent in highly populated parts of India. *Plasmodium vivax* forms hypnozoites during pre-erythrocytic cycle responsible for relapse. Perforin Like Protein 1 in *Plasmodium falciparum* helps in infection to erythrocytic cells by forming pore in membrane. Perforin Like protein 1 is cloned & expressed in BL21 (DE3) *E. coli* cells. PLP1 protein is purified by Immobilized metal ion affinity chromatography. This purified protein can be further analysed for role in hepatic cell invasion by *Plasmodium vivax* & it can be potential target for antimalarial against *Plasmodium vivax*.

सार

मलेरिया घातक बीमारी है जो प्लाज्मोडियम की विभिन्न प्रजातियों के कारण होती है। प्लाज्मोडियम फाल्सीपेरम और प्लाज्मोडियम विवाक्स भारत के अत्यधिक आबादी वाले हिस्सों में समान रूप से प्रचलित है। प्लाज्मोडियम विवाक्स का हैपेनोज़ोइट प्री-एरिथ्रोसाइटिक चक्र के दौरान अवशोषण के लिए जिम्मेदार बनता है। प्लाज्मोडियम फाल्सीपेरम प्रोटीन पीएलपी -1 छिद्रिन झिल्ली में छिद्र बनाकर एरिथ्रोसाइटिक कोशिकाओं में संक्रमण में मदद करता है। पीएलपी -1 प्रोटीन को क्लोन किया गया है और बीएल 21 (डीई 3) ई. कोलाई कोशिकाओं में व्यक्त किया गया है। पीएलपी 1 प्रोटीन इमोबिलाइज्ड धातु आयन एफ़िनिटी क्रोमैटोग्राफी द्वारा शुद्ध किया गया है। प्लाज्मोडियम विवाक्स द्वारा हेपेटिक सेल आक्रमण में भूमिका के लिए इस शुद्ध प्रोटीन का और विश्लेषण किया जा सकता है और यह प्लाज्मोडियम विवाक्स के खिलाफ एंटी-मलेरिया के लिए संभावित लक्ष्य हो सकता है।

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(Vinay Yadav)

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SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

%	Percent
°	Degree
C	Celsius
Min	Minute
hr	Hour
μM	Micromolar
mM	Millimolar
μl	Microliter
ml	Millilitre
ng	Nanogram
μg	Microgram
mg	Milligram
gm	Gram
W	Weight
g	Gyration
®	Registered
Psi	Pound per square inch
N	Nitryl terminal
C	Carboxyl terminal
α	Alpha
β	Beta
pH	Hydrogen potential
V	Voltage
O.D	Optical density
EDTA	Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid
IPTG	Isopropyl β-D-1-thiogalactopyranoside
MgCl ₂	Magnesium chloride
CaCl ₂	Calcium chloride
ZnCl ₂	Zinc chloride

CHAPTER 1

1.1 INTRODUCTION

Malaria is a disease caused by different species of Plasmodium, spread by infected female mosquito Anopheles' bite to healthy person [1]. Human population is infected by 5 species of Plasmodium named *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium ovale*, *Plasmodium malariae* and *Plasmodium knowlesi* but *Plasmodium vivax* is more prevalent in metro cities of India [2]. Malaria vectors, *Anopheles culicifacies*, is the major vector for rural malaria found all over the India and clean ground water collections is breeding place for them. *Anopheles stephensi* transmits malaria in urban areas, and it breeds in man-made water containers such as tanks, wells, cisterns by which parasite maintain its density for malaria transmission throughout the year [11]. *P. falciparum* is found worldwide in tropical and subtropical areas and especially predominates in Africa. *P. vivax* is found mostly in Asia, Latin America, and in some parts of Africa. In Asia it is the most prevalent human malaria parasite due to high population density. *P. malariae* is found worldwide [1,2]. Plasmodium completes its life cycle in two host- human and mosquito. Infected female anopheles mosquito inserts parasite (Sporozoite) into human body during meal uptake which reaches to liver through blood for replication & enters pre-erythrocytic cycle. Merozoite release from liver which enters to erythrocytic cycle where it infects erythrocytes & consumes haemoglobin for nutrition. During this cycle parasite develops different morphological forms such as ring, trophozoite, schizont & release as merozoite. Some merozoite re-infects other erythrocytes while other upon release from erythrocyte, some differentiate to form microgametocytes and macrogametocytes gametocytes. These gametocytes taken up by mosquito with the human blood during bite of female *Anopheles* mosquito & starts sporogony. Parasite moves to salivary gland of mosquito & develops as sporozoite. These sporozoites infects new healthy person [5]. *P. vivax* forms hypnozoites during pre-erythrocytic cycle which causes relapse. Wide variety of symptoms appears on infection from malaria, ranging from absent, very mild symptoms to severe disease and even death. High fevers, shaking chills, and flu-like illness is major symptoms of malaria [3].

Perforin like protein 1 expression by *Plasmodium falciparum* during erythrocytic stage which play role in erythrocytes invasion. Perforin Like protein 1 is secreted by microneme present at apical end of sporozoite & forms pore in erythrocytic cells [31]. However, this protein function is not reported in *P. vivax* till now & mechanism for this process is still not clear. Malaria parasite is developing resistance gradually to existing antimalarials drugs so there are requirements of new drug targets as well as new drugs.

1.2 AIM OF THE STUDY

To perform Gene cloning, expression and purification of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein-1 and protein. structure prediction, phylogenetic analysis.

1.3 OBJECTIVES

- i. Phylogenetic analysis of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1
- ii. Gene cloning, expression and purification of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1
- iii. *In silico* structure prediction of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1

2.1 Malaria

Life-threatening disease malaria is a vector borne disease, caused by protozoan parasite of genus *Plasmodium* in humans and animals that are transmitted by the bite of infected female *Anopheles* mosquito [1,2]. Female *Anopheles* mosquito is a bloodsucking insect, during a blood meal it ingests disease-producing microorganisms from an infected host (human) and later during their subsequent blood meal inject it into a new host [3].

Table 2.1 Taxonomic classification of Malaria Parasite

Kingdom	Protista
Sub-kingdom	Protozoa
Phylum	Apicomplexan
Class	Sporozoasida
Order	Eucoccidiorida
Family	Plasmodiidae
Genus	<i>Plasmodium</i>

2.1.1 Vectors

Anopheles culicifacies, is the major vector for rural malaria found all over India. *Anopheles stephensi* transmits malaria in urban area which breeds in man-made water containers such as tanks, wells, cisterns by which parasite maintain its density for malaria transmission throughout the year [3]. Human population gets infected by five *Plasmodium* species namely *Plasmodium falciparum*, *Plasmodium vivax*, *Plasmodium malariae*, *Plasmodium ovale*, and *Plasmodium knowlesi*.

2.1.2 Epidemiology

P. falciparum contributes to most of the deaths due to malaria. *P. falciparum* is found worldwide in tropical and subtropical areas and especially predominates in Africa

[1,3]. *P. falciparum* multiplies rapidly in blood which causes severe blood loss. *P. vivax* is found mostly in Asia, Latin America, and in some parts of Africa [2]. In Asia, it is the most prevalent human malaria parasite due to high population density. *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* has dormant liver stages known as hypnozoites which can activate and invade the blood in several months or years after the infecting mosquito bite and causes malarial relapses [1,2]. More than 17% of all infectious diseases are the vector-borne disease which leads to more than 700,000 deaths annually. 212 million cases were reported worldwide in 2016 which leads to 429,000 deaths, often children under 5 years of age come under this [3,4].

2.1.3 Symptoms

Wide variety of symptoms appears on infection from malaria, ranging from absent, very mild symptoms to severe disease and even death. High fevers, shaking chills, and flu-like illness is major symptoms of malaria. Malaria disease can be categorized into “uncomplicated or complicated” [3].

Uncomplicated Malaria:

This is rarely observed classical malaria which prolong up to 6 to 10 hours. Major symptoms are categories into 3 stages: 1). cold stage (sensation of shivering, cold), 2). hot stage (vomiting, fever, headache; seizures in young children), 3). sweating stage finally (sweats, tiredness, return to normal temperature). Elevated temperatures, weakness, enlarged spleen, perspiration, enlargement of the liver, mild jaundice observed in physical findings.

Severe malaria:

Multiple organ failures/abnormalities in the patient’s blood/impaired metabolism due to infection complications lead to the development of severe malaria. The manifestations of severe malaria include Cerebral malaria, Severe anaemia, Haemoglobinuria, Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), blood coagulation disorder, cardiovascular collapse, low blood pressure, Hyper-parasitaemia, Metabolic acidosis, hypoglycaemia etc.

2.1.4 Lifecycle

Malaria parasite infects two types of hosts one is “definitive host” that is female *Anopheles* mosquito and second is “intermediate host” human. Parasite multiplies at two stages in human firstly in hepatocytes and then in erythrocytes. Sporozoites are injected into the human body by malaria-infected female *Anopheles* mosquito during the blood meal.

Malaria Biology, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, Global Health- Division of Parasitic Disease and Malaria, 25-04-018.web.

31-05-2018

Figure 1.1 The life cycle of Malaria parasite [6]

Sporozoite infects hepatocytes, replicate there asexually, mature as schizont and release merozoite into the bloodstream. Sometimes parasite resides in dormant form as hypnozoites in hepatocytes which leads to the relapses up to one year or more [5]. Successive merozoites grow, forms ring stage trophozoites and develop to schizont, reproduce asexually, destroy the erythrocytes, releases merozoites and continues the

cycle by invading other erythrocytes (erythrocytic schizogony) [5]. *P. vivax* grows in the reticulocyte and greatly enlarges the host cell and increases its deformability [10]. These blood stage parasites responsible for symptoms of malaria. Upon release from erythrocyte, some parasites differentiate to form male (microgametocytes) and female (macrogametocytes) gametocytes. These gametocytes are taken up by female *Anopheles* mosquito during blood meal where parasite grows and replicates to starts a new cycle (sporogony). Parasite develops in the form of sporozoites (through zygote, motile ookinete, oocyst) in the salivary gland of female *Anopheles* mosquito after 10-18 days of blood feeding and these sporozoites are transmitted again in a healthy human [5].

2.2 *Plasmodium vivax*

During the ancient time the wild chimpanzees and gorillas throughout central Africa were endemically infected with parasites that are closely related to human *P. vivax* but due to point mutation duffy antigen receptor inhibition with due course of time parasite lost. *P. vivax* parasites are derived from a single ancestor that escaped out of Africa and but prevalent mostly in Asia, Latin America and few parts of Africa [8]. It is the most widely distributed cause of malaria, geographically with up to 2.5 billion people at risk and an estimated 80 million to 300 million clinical cases every year [10]. Due to very high population density in Asia, it is most prevalent among all 5 *Plasmodium* species [9]. About 50% of the malaria cases are due to *P. vivax* in the India [11]. Hypnozoite formation is one of the main reason for relapse and high prevalence. It helps to maintain genetic diversity. Asexual blood stage infects reticulocytes which leads to anaemia and low pyrogenic threshold. *P. vivax* can develop at lower temperature and it has shorter sporogenic cycle in mosquito female *Anopheles* which leads to easy transmission in temperate regions [9]. Mature gametocytes and asexual forms appear almost simultaneously so transmission occurs before appearance of symptoms. Low parasite density and early development of gametocytes are responsible for missed or delayed diagnosis [9].

2.3 Pre-erythrocytic cycle:

The sporozoites injected by mosquito move into the skin, enter blood vessels and reach to the liver within two to three hours of injection. Here parasite invade hepatocytes and transform into replicative exo-erythrocytic forms. These are the sites of parasite growth and replication until the development of the next invasive stage merozoites. These merozoites are released in the blood circulation and invade erythrocytes, causing the blood-stage infection [12].

2.3.1 Replication

Mosquito injects only a few dozen sporozoites into the skin and these sporozoite transforms into thousands of merozoites in liver. This phase is a crucial amplification stage for the establishment of parasite and cause the blood-stage infection. Sporozoites are 10 to 15 microns long polarized, elongated banana shaped cells. Complex pellicle is formed by the plasma membrane and the inner membrane complex with microtubules underneath the inner membrane complex. They have apical secretory organelles called the micronemes and the rhoptries which secrete their contents during parasite locomotion and host cell invasion [12].

2.3.2 Motility of Sporozoite

Sporozoites can move on solid substrates using gliding motility. Gliding is based on the release of adhesive proteins onto the surface of the apical end of the sporozoite. These can be translocated from the apical end to the rear end of the parasite by a parasite motor machinery called the glideosome. It is formed of a complex of proteins of the parasite located underneath the plasma membrane which includes a myosin motor, anchored in the inner membrane complex. Short actin filaments from the apical end of the parasite towards the end of the parasite is mobilized by myosin motor. Adhesin protein of parasite plasma membrane are connected to actin filaments. When the adhesins are engaged in interactions with the substrate (the surface of a host cell) forward

movement of the parasite occurs, due backward translocation of these actin adhesin complexes [13].

2.3.3 Traversal and productive invasion

P. berghei sporozoites must traverse cellular barriers in order to reach to hepatocytes. In the liver, they have to cross the endothelial cell, sinusoidal barrier and Kupffer cells. *P. berghei* Sporozoites can breach host hepatic cell membranes to traverse these cells. They form transient vacuoles during the traversal. Before switching to **productive invasion** mode *P. berghei* sporozoites migrate through several hepatocytes which leads to the formation of the membrane-bound parasite replicative compartment called the **parasitophorous vacuole** [14]. The cell passage and traversal over various murine cells in the liver sinusoids and dermis requires microneme secretory proteins [29]. During cell traversal, interaction of CD68 present on Kupffer cells with Glyceraldehyde 3- phosphate dehydrogenase present on parasite surface is required and during sporozoite invasion of hepatocytes receptor Ephrin A2 forms parasitophorous vacuole [27,28].

This process involves the formation of a specific structure called the **junction**. The *P. berghei* sporozoites actively glides through this junction to enter the hepatocyte inside an invagination of the host cell plasma membrane. It is an active process involving host and parasites entry factors, which are released from the secretory organelles such as the micronemes and the rhoptries. This leads to the formation of this compartment, called the **parasitophorous vacuole**. The parasitophorous vacuole membrane is the interface between the host cell and the parasite during liver-stage development. The membrane of the parasitophorous vacuole derives from the hepatocyte plasma membrane which is remodelled during entry, with the exclusion of most of the host cell transmembrane protein, and then during parasite development, with the insertion of parasite-derived membrane proteins [15]. During the productive invasion remodelling of the protein composition of vacuole membrane leads to

lysosome fusion resistant parasitophorous vacuole. The membrane of the vacuole is very important to protect the parasite from the host cells' defence mechanisms, and plays a role in the acquisition of nutrients, especially lipids required for parasite development [16]. The liver stage development is characterised by nuclear division without cell division process called **schizogony**. It occurs during the parasite maturation and merozoites formation, implies the coordinated partition of nuclei and organelles into the merozoites. Merozoites leave the liver in the form of merozoites. These are bags derived from the host cell membrane, that contain hundreds of merozoites. These are released in the blood circulation where they avoid phagocytosis by the liver macrophages. The merozoites are then released in the blood circulation and they can invade erythrocytes [17,18].

Some *Plasmodium* species such as *P. vivax* or *P. ovale* in humans can transform into dormant liver stages, called hypnozoites. Hypnozoites do not divide and stay quiescent for weeks to months in the liver. Hypnozoites are a problem for malaria control approaches because they cause malaria relapses long after the mosquito bite and they also form reservoirs of parasites that can contribute to malaria [19].

2.4 Perforin Like protein

Perforin like protein is conserved and expressed in every domain of life except Archaeobacteria. It is equally spread among Protista including Apicomplexa, Paramecium and Tetrahymena. Various Perforin like proteins (PLPs) are coded by Apicomplexans genome. PLP is expressed at different life stage of *Plasmodium* due to 2 different hosts- mosquito and human and play crucial role in parasite invasion, egression and motility [24]. Sporozoite travels from site of injection to hepatic cells through the skin (fibroblast, phagocytic cell) and liver capillaries (endothelial cells and sinusoidal endothelial cells). These PLPs have conserved membrane attack complex/perforins (MACPF) domain responsible for pore formation in target membrane (Bacterial pathogen and effector cells of immune system) [20]. Sporozoite traverse through kupffer cells with the help of PLP1, traversal lacking sporozoites are

more easily phagocytosed by macrophage in liver. Sporozoite traverse through low sulphated heparin sulphate proteoglycan (HSPGs) and invades high sulphated different β -plated sheet is present at N-terminal which helps in binding to target host membrane and C-terminal contains similar domain of variable length followed by unique β -plated sheet. Well conserved MACPF is present

Table 2.2 Perforin Like Proteins Types and their expression sites

Protein	Expression site
PPLP1	Sporozoites (Human hepatocytes invasion and traversal)
	Intra-erythrocytic development cycle
PPLP2	Permeabilization of the red blood cell membrane during egression
PPLP3	Ookinete (Mosquito midgut invasion)
PPLP4	Ookinete (Mosquito mid gut infection)
PPLP5	Ookinete (Mosquito midgut invasion)
	Sporozoite
	Gametocyte

between N and C terminal, localized to the microneme secretory organ of sporozoite apical region controlled by calcium ion similar to the calcium facilitated and directed release of perforin from secretory lysosomes of Natural Killer cells and Cytotoxic T lymphocytes [25]. *Plasmodium* breach host cell membrane during parasite outlet and cell traversal forming effector protein of the mammalian complement system C₆, C₇, C₈, C₉ and perforin was originally characterized as Perforin Like Protein [21]. During pore formation twisted β -plated sheet present on two helical cluster creates amphipathic β -hairpin which forms lower lining of the pore barrel on the surface of host membrane [26]. MACPF binds to surface of target cell and oligomerizes to form pre-pore complex which is followed by molecular rearrangement ultimately leads to

insertion in target host membrane to form large pores of approximate hundred angstroms diameter [22,23].

3.1 Chemicals, consumables & Equipment

Chemicals, consumables & Equipment used in this study are listed below

QiAMP DNA Mini Kit (Qiagen), Q5 High-Fidelity DNA Polymerase (NEB), dNTPs (GCC Biotech), HiPurA Plasmid DNA Miniprep Purification Kit (HIMEDIA), NucleoSpin Plasmid (MACHEREY-NAGEL), QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (QIAGEN), CoralLoad Concentrate (DNA Loading Dye), GeneRuler 1kb DNA Ladder (Thermo Scientific), Agarose, LB Broth, Terrific Broth, PCR Tubes, 1.5 ml Tubes, Falcon Tubes, Pipettes & Pipette Tips, Protein ladder (BIO-RAD), Tris-Cl (1.5 mM, pH 8.8), N,N,N',N'-tetramethylethylene-diamine (TEMED) (BIO-RAD), SDS 10%, APS (Ammonium persulfate) 10% (GCC Biotech), Acrylamide/Bis-acrylamide 30% (BIO-RAD). Gene primers were designed in lab and were commercially synthesized from GCC Biotech, India. DH5 α *E. coli* cells (Merck). Genomic DNA was extracted from vivax malaria patient blood from NIMR malaria clinic (approved from Ethical committee of NIMR).

3.2 Isolation of genomic DNA from *Plasmodium vivax* blood spot sample using QIAamp DNA Mini Kit

Buffer ATL 180 μ l was added to 3 punched-out circles from a dried blood spot and incubated at 85°C for 10 min. Proteinase K 20 μ l stock solution was added and incubated at 56°C for 1 hr. Buffer AL 200 μ l was added to the sample and mixed thoroughly by vortexing and incubated at 70°C for 10 min. Briefly centrifuge to remove drops from inside the lid. Absolute ethanol was added to the sample and mixed thoroughly by vortexing. This mixture was applied on QIAamp Mini spin column and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 1 min. QIAamp Mini spin column was placed in a clean Eppendorf tube for 1 min. QIAamp Mini spin column was placed in a clean 2 ml collection tube and added 500 μ l Buffer AW2, centrifuged at full speed 14,000 rpm

for 3 min. QIAamp Mini spin column was placed in a new 2 ml collection tube centrifuged at full speed for 1 min. Buffer AE 150 µl was added and Incubated at room temperature for 1 minute and then centrifuged 8000 rpm for 1 min. This eluted DNA was stored at -20°C for further use 2 ml collection tube. Buffer AW1 500 µl was added and centrifuged at 8000

3.3 Amplification of *Plasmodium vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 (*PvPlp1*) gene by Polymerase chain reaction

Gradient PCR was done using genomic DNA from *Plasmodium vivax* blood spot sample following PCR methodology. At first a 100 µl of Master mix was prepared using 0.5 µM each of Forward (PvPLP1Fpa) and Reverse (PvPLP1Rp) primers, 8 µl of Template DNA, Q5 HiFi DNA polymerase, 5X Q5 reaction buffer, 10 mM dNTPs.

Table.3.1 Composition of Master mix for Q5 High Fidelity DNA polymerase PCR reaction

Components	Quantity for 100 µl Reaction	Final Concentration
5X Q5 Reaction Buffer	20 µl	1X concentration
10 mM dNTPs	2 µl	200 mM
10 µM Forward Primer	5 µl	0.5 µM
10 µM Reverse Primer	5 µl	0.5 µM
Template DNA	8 µl	<1,000 ng
Q5 High Fidelity DNA Polymerase	1 µl	0.02 U/µl
5x Q5 High GC Enhancer	39 µl	1x concentration
Nuclease Free Water	20 µl	

Q5 High fidelity DNA, neb, New England biolabs, 2018.web.31-0502018

Primers:

Gene primers were designed in lab & were commercially Synthesized from GCC Biotech, India.

Table 3.2 Details of primers for *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1

S. No.	Name	Sequence (5'-3')	Length	Restriction enzyme	Restriction site
1	PvPL P1Fpa	5'- TTCCATATGGA CACACCCAGCG ATG -3'	24	NdeI	5'-CA'TATG- 3' 3'-GTAT,AC-5'
2	PvPL P1Rp	5'- TACTCGAGTCA ATGATGGTGAT GGTGATGCTTC TGAGCCAACCT -3'	44	XhoI	5'-C'TCGAG- 3' 3'-GAGCTC-5'

The cycling conditions were as initial denaturation at 98°C for 30 seconds, 30 cycles of denaturation at 98°C for 7 seconds, annealing at 55°C-70°C for 20 seconds, extension at 72°C, Final extension at 72°C for 2 minutes, Infinite Hold at 10°C. Gradient PCR temperature was 55°-70°C.

The PCR was performed by using BIO-RAD T¹⁰⁰ Thermal Cycler. The amplified PCR product were separated on 1% Agarose gel and stained with ethidium bromide(10 mg/ml) to visualize under UV using Gel Documentation System (UVITech 1D). A gene product size for 2007 bp was considered as amplified product by comparing with Thermo scientific GeneRuler 1kb DNA ladder (0.5 µg/µL).

3.4 DNA Extraction [QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (250)]

Amplified Gene fragment of *PvPlp1* was cut from the Agarose gel with a clean, sharp scalpel and weighed gel slice in a 1.5 ml tube. Added 3 volumes of Buffer QG to 1 volume of gel (100 mg~100 μ l). Incubated at 50°C for 10 minutes (or until the gel slice had completely dissolved) and 1 gel volume of isopropanol was added to the sample and mixed. To bind DNA, applied the sample to the QIAquick column and centrifuged for 1 minute at 11000 rpm. Discarded flow through and then added 0.5 ml of Buffer QG to QIAquick column and centrifuged for 1 minute. To wash, added 0.75 ml of Buffer PE to QIAquick column and centrifuged for 1 minute at 11000 rpm. Discarded the flow through and centrifuged the QIAquick column for an additional 1 minute at \geq 13000 rpm. DNA was eluted with 50 μ l Buffer EB (10 mM Tris-Cl, pH 8.5) in 1.5 ml microfuge tube by centrifugation of the column for 1 minute at maximum speed.

Estimated concentration 15.8-17.7 ng/ μ l was done using Nanodrop.

[QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (250)]

3.5 Cloning

Restriction digestion

All components of reaction were thawed on ice and prepared reaction mix of 40 μ l volume in a microfuge tube. Added all reagents in following order: 32 μ l (512ng) of purified PCR product, 10 units of Nde1, 10 units of Xho1, 1X smart Buffer. Gently mixed by tapping tube and short spin to settle tube content and then typically incubated at 37°C for 45 minutes. The digested sample were checked on 1% Agarose gel and run at 100V for 1 hour.

DNA Extraction [QIAquick Gel Extraction Kit (250)] was done in 32 μ l of Buffer EB as described in section 3.5, Estimated DNA concentration was 34.5-42.8 ng/ μ l using Nanodrop method.

Ligation of gene *PvPlp1* in vector pET22b+ (NEB)

Complete reaction was set up on ice in the microfuge tube. Gently mixed the reaction by pipetting up and down and microfuge briefly. For sticky ends, incubated at room temperature overnight.

T4 DNA ligation of perforin like protein 1 + pET22b vector:

Concentration of pET22b = 8 ng/ μ l

Concentration of insert DNA = 30 ng/ μ l

COMPONENTS	LIGATION RATIO (1:3)	LIGATION RATIO (1:6)	LIGATION RATIO (1:9)
Insert DNA	0.9 μ l	1.6 μ l	2.4 μ l
Vector DNA	1 μ l	1 μ l	1 μ l
T4 DNA Ligase Buffer (10X)	2 μ l	2 μ l	2 μ l
T4 DNA Ligase	1 μ l	1 μ l	1 μ l
Nuclease Free Water	15.1 μ l	14.4 μ l	13.6 μ l
Total	20 μ l	20 μ l	20 μ l

Table 1.3 Ligation reaction components and concentration

Adopted from <https://www.neb.com/-/media/catalog/datacards-or.../m0202datasheet-lot1071207.pdf>

3.6 Transformation

Preparation of Chemically Competent DH5 α Cells of *E. coli*

Streaked a loopful culture of DH5 α cells on LB Agar plate and incubated at 37°C overnight. Second day, inoculated a single colony in 10 ml LB broth and grown at 37°C overnight. Next day, inoculated 2 ml culture in 200 ml LB Broth and grown at 37°C shaker till the optical density $_{600}$ reached 0.35-0.4. Immediately placed the culture flask on ice for 30 minutes. The cells were harvested at 4000 rpm for 15 minutes. Discarded supernatant and gently suspended pellet in 15 ml of cold 10 mM MgCl₂ and spin at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. Discarded supernatant and re-suspended the pellet in 40 ml of 10 mM CaCl₂. Kept on ice for 20 minutes. Harvest the cells at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. Discarded supernatant again and re-suspended pellet in ~25 ml ice cold 85 mM CaCl₂, 15% glycerol. Harvested the cells at 3000 rpm for 15 minutes at 4°C. Discarded supernatant and re-suspended pellet in 1 ml ice cold 85 mM CaCl₂ and 15% glycerol (the final O.D.₆₀₀ = ~200-250). Aliquots 50 μ l into 1.5 ml tube, snap freeze with Liquid N₂ and stored at -80°C freezer and checked transformation efficiency of competent cells.

Preparation of LB Agar plates and LB Broth

Luria Bertani Agar plate:

Dissolved LB Agar powder (30.5 g/1000 ml) in deionized water and autoclaved the liquid medium at 121°C, 15 psi for 15 minutes. Cool down the medium to 55°C and antibiotic ampicillin (1 μ g/ml) was added and pour into petri-dishes. Let it solidify, then inverted and stored at 4°C in the dark.

Luria Bertani Broth:

Dissolved appropriate amount of LB powder (15.5 gm/1000 ml) in deionized water. Autoclaved the liquid medium at 121°C or 15 psi for 15 minutes. Allowed the solution to cool down to 55°C and ampicillin (1 μ g/ml) was added and stored at 4°C.

Transformation of *PvPlp1* clone in competent DH5 α cells of *E. coli* strain:

Transferred the LB Broth and LB Agar plate 4°C to room temperature. 10 μ l of competent DH5 α cells was added to *PvPlp1* clone. Mixed well and incubated on ice

for 30 minutes followed by heat shock at 42°C for 45 seconds. Cells were incubated on ice for another 2 minutes. Then 200 µl LB medium was added and incubated at 37°C for 1 hour shaking at 220 rpm. Aliquots of suspension were spread on LB agar plate amp⁺. The plates were incubated at 37°C overnight. Single colonies were picked up and inoculated in 2 ml LB broth amp⁺ (1 µg/ml) for confirmation by plasmid isolation on the following day. The medium incubated at 37°C for 6-8 hours. The cloning was confirmed by colony PCR.

Colony PCR:

A colony from an agar plate was picked and transferred to a 0.5 ml tube containing 50 µl of sterile water and Vortex to disperse the cells. The tube was placed at heat block at 99°C for 5 min to lyse the cells and denature DNases. Centrifugation was done at 12,000 × g for 1 min and 10 µl of the supernatant was transferred to PCR tubes. Left on ice until use. Master mix was added to sample containing 0.5 µM each of Forward (PvPLP1Fpa) and Reverse (PvPLP1Rpa) primers, 1µl Q5 HiFi DNA polymerase, mixed gently and placed the samples in a thermal cycler. The cycling conditions were as initial denaturation at 98°C for 30 seconds, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 98°C for 7 seconds, annealing at 64°C for 20 seconds, extension at 72°C, Final extension at 72°C for 2 minutes, infinite Hold at 10°C.

3.7 Isolation of clone from DH5α cells:

For cultivation of bacterial cells plasmids, the cell colony was inoculated in Terrific growth medium amp⁺ and incubated at 37°C with constant shaking 220 rpm for overnight.

1 ml of a saturated *E. coli* Terrific broth culture were pellet down in a standard benchtop microcentrifuge for 30 s at 11,000xg. Supernatant was discarded and buffer A1 250 µl was added to resuspend the cell pellet completely by vortexing. Buffer A2 250 µl was added, mixed gently by inverting the tube 6–8 times and Incubated at room

temperature for 5 minutes. Then buffer A3 300 μ l was added and mixed thoroughly by inverting the tube 6–8 times until blue samples turned colorless. Centrifuged for 5 min at 11,000 xg at room temperature. Supernatant of 750 μ l was transferred to NucleoSpin® Plasmid Column and centrifuged for 1 min at 11,000xg. Flow through was discarded and placed the NucleoSpin® Plasmid Column back into the collection tube. Buffer A4 600 μ l (supplemented with ethanol) was added and Centrifuged for 1 min at 11,000 x g. Flow through was discarded and placed the NucleoSpin® Plasmid Column back into the empty collection tube. Silica membrane was dried by centrifugation for 2 min at 11,000 x g and collection tube was discarded. The NucleoSpin® Plasmid Column was placed in a 1.5 mL microcentrifuge tube and 50 μ l Buffer AE was added. Incubation was given for 1 min at room temperature and then centrifuged for 1 min at 11,000 x g to collect plasmid. Eluted plasmid was placed at -20°C.

3.8 Preparation of BL21(DE3) *E. coli* competence cells and transformation of *PvPlp1* pET22b+ vector

Preparation of competence cells and transformation was done by process as shown in section 3.7

3.9 Protein Expression

Primary inoculation:

Perforin Like Protein 1 transformed BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells were picked from Agar Plate and inoculated in 3 ml LB media amp⁺(100 μ g/ml). This inoculum was kept at 37°C, 220 rpm for overnight.

Secondary inoculation:

Overnight grown culture was inoculated to 50 ml Terrific Growth medium (1% glycerol, 5 μ M ZnCl₂, 0.1% glycerol) with 1% inoculum size. This inoculum was kept at 37°C, 220 rpm until O.D.₆₀₀ reaches 0.4-0.6 until cells reaches log phase of growth curve.

Induction:

Cells at log Phase were induced by Isopropyl β -D-1-thiogalactosidase (IPTG) 1 mM concentration and grown for 6 hours at 37°C, 220 rpm.

The cells were pellet down by centrifugation at 7,000 rpm for 20 minutes and stored at -20°C.

3.10 Cell Lysis

Recombinant protein PvPLP1 expressed BL21(DE3) cells were lysed after expression was done to harvest the protein. Whole process was performed at ice. Cell Lysis buffer (Tris 0.3 M, NaCl 0.04 M, pH-7.5) 2 ml was added to cell pellet and resuspended completely. Sonication of the sample was done at 20 Kilo hertz for 10 seconds 6 cycle followed by 2-minute break after each cycle to cool down. Centrifugation of sample was done at 14,000 rpm for 30 minutes. Supernatant was collected in separate microfuge tube and stored at -20°C for further use.

3.11 SDS-PAGE

Separating gel 10% solution was prepared for 74 kDa protein with composition given in table 3.4 in 50 ml falcon tube and mixed properly by swirling the solution gently and thoroughly. Appropriate amount of separating solution was aspirated and casted in the gap between glass plates. The top of separating gel was filled with isopropanol to make the top of gel horizontally even and left for 30 minutes to polymerize. Discarded the isopropanol after gelation and left for air dry.

Table 3.4 SDS-PAGE separating gel 12% composition

Chemical name	volume
Acrylamide/Bis-acrylamide(30%/0.8%w/v)	4 ml
1.5M Tris, p.H-8.8	2.6 ml
10%(w/v) SDS	0.1 ml
10%(w/v) ammonium persulfate (APS)	0.1 ml
Tetramethylene-diamine (TEMED)	0.01 ml
Double distilled water	3.2 ml

Stacking gel was prepared with composition given in table no.3.5 and mixed properly by swirling the solution gently and thoroughly. Appropriate amount of stacking solution was aspirated and in the gap between glass plates until overflow. Well forming comb was inserted without trapping air under the teeth and left for 30 minutes to polymerize.

Table 3.5 Composition of 5% SDS-PAGE stacking gel

Chemical name	Volume
Tris-cl, pH-6.8	5 ml (1M stock)
SDS	2 gm
Glycerol	11.5 ml
EDTA pH-8.0	5 ml (0.5M stock)
Bromophenol blue	20 mg
β -mercapto -ethanol	1 ml

After polymerization comb were taken out and gel plates placed in the cell buffer dam. Running buffer (25 mM Tris, 200 mM glycine) was poured in inner chamber till the overflow and until the buffer reaches marked level. Protein sample was mixed with 4x loading buffer and boiled at 100°C for 10 minutes. Samples and protein ladder was loaded on gel and run at 100 volts for 60 minutes.

Staining:

Stacking gel was excised out after resolution of protein and resolving gel was stained with Coomassie blue. Gel was stained with Coomassie blue and incubated on gel rocker for 1hr at room temperature. After that destain solution (40% methanol and 10% glacial acetic acid) incubated for 1hr on gel rocker at room temperature. Results was observed after detaining.

3.12 Western Blotting

10% gel was prepared and protein was resolved as described in section 3.12. Before transferring of protein membrane, gel, filter papers were equilibrated in transfer buffer. Gel and membrane sandwich was prepared as showing in figure 3.1. Sandwich cassette was placed in module by matching electrode terminal and frozen ice-cooling unit and stir bar were placed in tank filled with chilled transfer buffer (25 mM tris, 192 mM glycine, 20% methanol). Transfer was done at 100V for 60 minutes on magnetic stirrer.

Figure 3.1 Gel sandwich assembly

After transfer of protein, membrane was blocked with 5% fat free milk in 1x PBS for 60 minutes shaking at room temperature followed by 3 washes of 1x PBS for 10 minutes shaking each. Membrane was incubated with his-tagged primary antibody diluted (1:5000) in 1% BSA for 60 minutes shaking at room temperature. Three times washing of membrane was done by 1x PBST for 10 minutes shaking. Membrane was incubated with HRP conjugated secondary antibody diluted (1:2500) in 1x PBS for 60 minutes shaking at room temperature and Three times washing of membrane was done by 1x PBST for 10 minutes shaking. Protein band development was done by 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) which gives blue colour when incubated with HRP. Protein band size was observed on membrane and image was captured.

3.13 Bulk expression of protein and cell lysis

Bulk expression of protein for culture volume 500 ml was done as described in section 3.10. Cell lysis was done as described in section 3.11 with extended time period of 20 seconds.

3.14 Purification of protein

Purification of protein was done by using Nickel-Immobilized metal affinity chromatography (Ni-IMAC).

Preparation of column

Column bed was prepared by 3 ml Nickel agarose beads slurry. These columns were settled and equilibrated by washing buffer (40 mM Tris, 300 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole)

Purification

Nickel column was washed with distilled water of 3 bed volume (9 ml) and cell lysis supernatant was loaded on column and flow through was collected in falcon tube. First Washing was done by 12 ml washing buffer A (40 mM Tris, 300 mM NaCl, 20 mM imidazole) and flow through was collected in 15 ml falcon tube. Washing 2nd, 3rd, 4th,

5th was done by 12 ml, 8 ml, 6 ml, 6 ml, washing buffer having 50 mM, 100 mM, 150 mM, 200 mM, imidazole respectively and collected flow through in fresh 15 ml falcon tube. Final elution was done by 1.5 ml elution buffer having 300 mM imidazole concentration and flow through was collected in fresh falcon tube. Confirmation of purification was done by running gel on SDS-PAGE and by Western blot as described in section 3.12 and 3.13.

Recharge of Nickel beads column

Nickel beads were washed in 5 column volumes of nanopure water. Column was washed with 3 column volume of Strip buffer (100 mM EDTA, 500 mM Tris, pH 8.0) which leads beads colour to white. Nickel beads column was washed again with nanopure water. After washing Nickel beads were charged by 3 column volume of charge buffer (100 mM NiCl₂). Nickel beads were then washed with nanopure water. Again, washed with binding buffer and stored in 20% ethanol at 4°C for further use.

3.15 *In-silico* analysis of *Plasmodium vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 (PvPLP1)

Evolutionary analysis

Protein sequence of PvPLP1 was retrieved from National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) protein database in FASTA format. Protein protein basic local alignment search tool (BLASTp) was used to retrieve similar protein sequence of Apicomplexa phylum from nonredundant protein sequence database and Uncultured/environmental sample sequences, models were excluded. Query coverage cut off value was set to 95%, putative and hypothetical protein sequence were excluded from blast hit and 15 proteins were selected for further evolutionary analysis.

Table 3.7 Proteins detail for evolutionary analysis

Query	Sequence	Identity	Length	Mismatch	gap open	Query start	Query end	E-value	Bit Score	% positive
gi 156097	EDL45240.	100	668	0	0	1	668	0	1390	100
gi 156097	SCO71305	100	668	0	0	1	668	0	1390	100
gi 156097	KMZ81828	98.952	668	1	1	1	668	0	1370	98.95
gi 156097	GAB65199	78.152	682	128	3	1	666	0	1082	85.78
gi 156097	ANQ06730	76.716	670	116	4	1	664	0	1058	84.63
gi 156097	CAQ38668	74.74	673	141	4	1	667	0	1038	83.95
gi 156097	SBS81152.	54.656	655	266	8	17	661	0	740	73.28
gi 156097	KYO00785	50	646	295	5	19	661	0	676	69.5
gi 156097	SBS99413.	47.977	692	313	6	14	661	0	662	66.04
gi 156097	SOV78537	50.31	646	288	7	21	661	0	658	69.04
gi 156097	SCM05311	46.828	662	315	8	16	662	0	651	67.37
gi 156097	ETB56531.	47.409	656	318	7	18	660	0	648	67.84
gi 156097	CDS45728.	46.606	663	321	8	16	662	0	646	67.27
gi 156097	GAW7971.	58.99	495	180	3	23	517	0	598	73.33
gi 156097	GAW7971.	63.871	155	56	0	507	661	4.74E-63	227	80.65

These 15 Proteins sequences were saved in FASTA format for alignment. MEGA7 was used for alignment of sequences using Multiple Sequence Comparison by Log-Expectation (MUSCLE) default alignment method and saved in FASTA format. Evolutionary tree was constructed using Maximum Likelihood method by default parameters.

Protein tertiary structure prediction

Protein sequence of PvPLP1 was retrieved from National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) protein database in FASTA format. This protein sequence was submitted to protein Homology/analogy Recognition Engine v 2.0 (phyre2) protein structure prediction online tool that works on intensive homology modelling mode. Protein structure file was saved in pdb format.

4.1 Amplification of *Plasmodium vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 (*PvPlp1*) gene

Gradient Polymerase chain reaction was setup for amplification of *PvPlp1* gene and amplification was observed at 57.9-75°C annealing temperature as shown in figure 4.1 but primer dimers were observed at 68.9 & 70°C, so gene amplified at 64°C chosen for further process.

Figure 4.1 Amplification of *PvPlp1* by PCR, M- Generuler 1kb DNA ladder, Thermo Scientific #SM0314, 0.1ug/ul, 1- Gradient PCR annealing temp. 70°C, 2- Gradient PCR annealing temp. 68.9°C, 3- Gradient PCR annealing temp. 67.0°C, 4- Gradient PCR annealing temp. 64.0°C, 5- Gradient PCR annealing temp. 60.7°C, 6- Gradient PCR annealing temp. 57.9°C, 7- Gradient PCR temperature 56.1°C

4.2 Restriction digestion of Plasmid (pET22b+) and insert (*PvPlp1*)

Restriction digestion of plasmid and insert was done to insert gene in vector and confirmed by resolving on 1% Agarose as shown in figure 4.2

Figure 4.2 Restriction digestion of plasmid and insert, C-Control Sample, M- Generuler 1kb DNA ladder, Thermo Scientific #SM0314, 0.1ug/ul, 1- Plasmid pET22b+, 2- Plasmid pET22b+ and insert *PvPlp1*

4.3 Cloning of *PvPlp1* pET22b+ in Dh5 α *E. coli* cells

Insert *PvPlp1* was ligated in pET22b+ & transformed in Dh5 α *E. coli* cells. These cells were plated on Luria Bertani agar Amp⁺ plate. Cell colonies were observed after 24 hours on agar plate as shown in figure 4.3

Figure 4.3 Dh5 α *E. coli* cells cloned with *PvPlp1* pET22b+

4.4 Colony PCR

Cloning was confirmed by Colony PCR of *PvPlp1* clone at 64°C & Amplification of gene was detected as shown in figure 4.4

Figure 4.4 Colony PCR Amplification at 64°C, M - Generuler 1kb DNA ladder, Thermo Scientific #SM0314,0.1ug/ul, 1 to 5- Amplified *PvPlp1* gene Band

4.5 Isolation of *PvPlp1* clone & Transformation to BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells

Plasmid with *PvPlp1* gene was isolated and transformed to BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells for expression as shown in figure 4.5 and 4.6

Figure 4.5 *PvPlp1* clone with pET22b+ on Agarose gel, M- Generuler 1kb DNA ladder, Thermo Scientific #SM0314,0.1ug/ul, P- *PvPlp1* clone

Transformation was done in BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells & colonies were observed on Luria Bertani medium agar plates as shown in figure 4.6

Figure 4.6 BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells after cloning of *PvPlp1* pET22b+ on LB Agar Plate

4.6 Expression of *Plasmodium vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 in BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells

Expression of PvPLP1 was done in BL21(DE3) *E. coli* cells confirmed by SDS-PAGE Coomassie staining shown in figure 4.7

Figure 4.7 Expression of PvPLP1 on SDS-PAGE, M- Protein marker, BIO-RAD #161-0374, 1- Protein induced by 2 mM concentration, 2- Protein induced by 1.5 mM concentration, 3- Protein induced by 1 mM concentration, 4- Protein induced by 0.5 mM concentration

Multiple bands were observed on SDS-PAGE to confirm the expression western blot was done.

Western Blot of Perforin like protein 1

PvPLP1 protein band was observed above 75 KDa protein marker band, band intensity of band increases with increasing IPTG concentration.

Figure 4.8 Expression of PvPLP1 on Western Blot, M - Protein marker, BIO-RAD #161-0374, NC- Negative control, 1- Protein induced by 0.5 mM concentration of IPTG, 2- Protein induced by 1 mM concentration of IPTG, 3- Protein induced by 1.5 mM concentration of IPTG

4.7 Purification of protein

Protein purification was done using Ion metal exchange chromatography (IMAC) & confirmed by SDS-PAGE and Western blot as shown in figure 4.9 & 4.10

Figure 4.9 Purification of PvPLP1 IMAC on SDS-PAGE, M- Protein marker, BIO-RAD #161-0374, L - Cell lysate, F - Flow through protein purification column, 1-Wash with 20 mM Imidazole concentration, 2 - Wash with 50 mM Imidazole concentration, 3-Wash with 100 mM Imidazole concentration, 4-Wash with 150 mM Imidazole concentration, 5-Wash with 200 mM Imidazole concentration, E-Wash with 300 mM Imidazole concentration

Western Blot:

Figure 4.10 Purification of *PvPLP1* by IMAC on SDS-PAGE, L - Cell lysate, F - Flow through protein purification column, 1 - Wash with 20 mM Imidazole concentration, 2 - Wash with 50 mM Imidazole concentration, 3 - Wash with 100 mM Imidazole concentration, 4 - Wash with 150 mM Imidazole concentration, 5 - Wash with 200 mM Imidazole concentration, E - Wash with 300 mM Imidazole concentration, M- Protein marker, BIO-RAD #161-0374

4.8 *In-silico* analysis

4.8.1 Evolutionary analysis of Perforin like protein1

Molecular evolutionary genetic analysis (MEGA7) software was used to build evolutionary tree using Maximum Likelihood method by default parameters as shown in figure 4.11. Evolutionary analysis shows the protein PvPLP1 and *Plasmodium vivax* Perforin Like Protein 4 are most related sequence. PvPLP4 play crucial role for infection of the mosquito midgut by mediating ookinete traversal through the midgut epithelium by parasite.

Figure 4.11 Evolutionary tree of PvPLP1 Protein

4.8.2 Perforin Like Protein 1 tertiary structure prediction

Protein homology/analogy recognition engine (Phyre2) was used for protein tertiary structure prediction using homology modelling gives protein structure that is similar to *Toxoplasma gondii* perforin-like protein 1 as shown in figure 4.12

Figure 4.12 Predicted tertiary structure of PvPLP1

This protein composed of 2 domain having barrel shape structure as shown in figure 4.13. The *Toxoplasma gondii* PLP1 (TgPLP1) is required for efficient exit from parasitophorous vacuoles. Two different domain structures are similar to hexameric membrane attack complex/perforin (MACPF), it contains 2 helix, 15 beta sheets and Apicomplexan PLP C-terminal β -pleated sheet (APC β) domains contains 10 helix, 8 beta sheets of TgPLP1 [32].

Figure 4.13 Domains of PvPLP1 predicted structure

Detail for predicted binding site for protein is given in table 4.1

Table 4.1 Predicted binding site of PvPLP1 Protein

Serial no.	Residue	Amino Acid
1.	438	ARG
2.	439	VAL
3.	440	ARG
4.	443	ALA
5.	444	ALA
6.	445	LYS
7.	446	GLY
8.	447	ARG
9.	448	ASP
10.	501	ASN
11.	528	ARG

Figure 4.14 Predicted binding of PvPLP1 protein

Cloning & expression of *Plasmodium vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 was done in *Escherichia coli* (DE3) cells and purification of protein was done by immobilized metal anion exchange chromatography. This is earlier reported that ortholog of Perforin Like Protein 1 play role in hepatic cells traversal by *P. berghei* & *P. yoeli* sporozoites during pre-erythrocytic cycle [15]. Protein band observed on SDS-PAGE & Western blot seems similar to Perforin Like Protein 1 of *Plasmodium berghei* and *P. yoeli* earlier reported & may have similar role in traversal of sporozoite.

Structural evolutionary analysis was also done for protein of interest with proteins of Apicomplexa phylum. Evolutionary tree shows that Perforin Like Protein 1 is present in same clade of Perforin Like Protein 4 of *Plasmodium vivax* which plays important role in Mosquito mid gut infection [33].

Tertiary structure prediction was also done for Perforin Like Protein 1 similar to *Toxoplasma gondii* perforin-like protein 1 of *Toxoplasma gondii* [32]. This information can be further utilized for protein structure resolution & Further studies are required for confirmation of protein & structure analysis.

Cloning, expression and purification of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein was successfully done and confirmed by western blot. Phylogenetic analysis of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 was successfully done showing this protein sequence is more similar to Perforin Like Protein 4 of *P. vivax*. *In silico* structure prediction of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1 gives protein structure that is similar to *Toxoplasma gondii* Perforin-Like Protein 1. These *in-silico* results can be further used for solving structure of *P. vivax* Perforin Like Protein 1. This protein can be further utilized for drug, vaccine development.

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2018

Personal Profile

Name : Vinay Yadav
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Permanent address : Near Kheta Nath Temple
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India, 123021

EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION

- Pursuing **Masters of Science in Microbiology** Final year **61%** marks
- **Bachelors of Science in Microbiology** (2013-16) with **63.58%** marks
- **Senior Secondary Education** CBSE (2011-12) with securing **76.6%** marks
- **High school Education** CBSE (2009-10) with securing **77.9%** marks

AREAS OF INTEREST:

Microbiology, Molecular biology, Recombinant DNA Technology, Immunology, Industrial microbiology, Parasitology & infectious disease

POST GRADUATE THESIS TOPIC

Cloning, expression and purification of gene expressing at Pre-erythrocytic stage of *Plasmodium vivax* life cycle

MAJOR COURSES UNDERGONE:

Molecular Biology: DNA replication, Recombinant and repair of DNA, Transcription, Post-transcription process (Splicing, Capping), Translation, Post-translation processes, Molecular basis of cell physiology.

Biochemistry: Enzymology- characteristics of enzymes, Activation energy, Factors influencing catalytic efficiency, Enzyme kinetics, Rapid Equilibrium, significance of K_m , Lineweaver-Burk plot, Effect of pH on enzyme stability and activity, Effect of temperature on enzyme stability, Arrhenius equation, Regulation of enzyme activity: Feedback inhibition, allosteric concept, Application of enzymes in analytical labs. (clinical and industrial), enzymes as industrial catalysts, Immobilized enzymes, assay of enzyme activities for diagnostic purposes, abzymes, recent developments.

Immunology: Detailed structure and development of B cell (Ig) and T cell (TcR) receptors, Pattern Recognition Receptors (PRRs) and Toll-like receptors (TLR); Markers of suppressor / regulatory cells - CD4+ CD25+ Foxp3+ Treg, iNKT, Humoral and cell-mediated immune response; Innate immune response and pattern recognition; Recent advances in innate immune response especially NK-DC interactions, Tolerance and autoimmunity, Transplantation and tumor immunology:

Recombinant DNA technology: Basics of DNA cloning, Methods of DNA and protein analysis Polymerase Chain Reaction, Construction of cDNA and genomic DNA libraries, Genome sequencing, Transcriptional analysis of gene expression and transcriptomics, Overexpression of recombinant proteins, Analysis of protein-DNA and protein-protein interactions, Protein engineering and proteome analysis, Pharmaceutical products of DNA technology, Transgenics and animal cloning.

Microbial Genetics: Genetic analysis of bacteria, Gene transfer and mapping by conjugation, Lytic bacteriophages, Gene transfer by transformation and transduction, Lysogenic phages, Transposons, Gene regulation.

Bioinformatics, Industrial Microbiology, Microbial Physiology and Metabolism, Environmental Microbiology.

CERTIFICATE COURSES

- Diploma course on **Microbial Biotechnology** under the **GLOBAL INITIATIVE OF ACADEMIC NETWORKS (GIAN)** scheme of **MHRD** in 2016
- Diploma course on **Membrane Processes for Water, Food and Biotech Applications** under the **GLOBAL INITIATIVE OF ACADEMIC NETWORKS (GIAN)** scheme of **MHRD** in 2017
- Certificate course on “**General course on intellectual property**” conducted by **WIPO** in 2017
- Six-week MOOC course on **Tuberculosis** conducted by **Institute Pasteur, Paris, France**
- Six-week MOOC course on **Malaria** conducted by **Institute Pasteur, Paris, France**

Seminar and workshops

- Attended University of Delhi’s **Gyanodaya – IV** educational tour in March 2014.
- Attended a workshop on the **technology-based incubator** at South Campus, University of Delhi in 2015
- Industrial visit to **Yakult** at **Sonipat** & “**Mushroom cultivation**” at **HAIC Integrated Mushroom Research & Development Center** at Murthal in 2014
- Attended workshop on **viral cultivation strategies** at Bhaskaracharya college of Applied Sciences, DU in 2015
- Attended one-day symposium on “**Biofuels: An alternative and Nonconventional Energy source for future**” at Central University of Haryana in 2016
- Attended a national symposium on **Infectious diseases, advancement in diagnosis, therapeutics and vaccines** at Bhaskaracharya college of Applied Sciences, Delhi University in 2014.
- Attended a symposium on **antibiotic resistance: A major global threat and Annual microbiology festival Microquest** at Bhaskaracharya college of Applied Sciences, Delhi University in 2016.
- Attended National seminar on **Biotechnology for sustainable development** at Central University of Haryana in 2016
- Attended National seminar on **Microbes for human health and environment** at Central University of Haryana in 2016
- Attended Lecture by **prof. T.P. Singh, INSA senior scientist AIIMS, New Delhi** on **protein structure and Ramachandran plot** at Central University of Haryana in 2017
- Attended seminar lecture on **Isolation of cellulose degrading Thermophilic fungi** by **Bhupinder chadda, professor Gurunanak Dev University, Amritsar** at Central University of Haryana in 2017
- Attended one-day colloquium on “**structure of DNA: Away forward to Genomic Revolution**” at Central University of Haryana on 25th April 2017

- Summer internship project at JNU on “**sequence and phylogeny analysis**” in June-July 2017
- Attended seminar lecture on “**DNA damage Repair**” by **Lei Li ,MD Anderson cancer centre, Department of radiation oncology** at Central University of Haryana Feb 2018
- Attended open seminar lecture on “**Targeting *Plasmodium vivax* challenges & opportunities**” by **Ivo Mueller, malaria: parasites and hosts, Department of Parasites and Insect Vector, Institute Pasteur, Paris, France** at National Institute of Malaria Research on 20 March 2018
- Attended open seminar lecture on “**Development of vaccine for plasmodium vivax based duffy bindo**” by **Chetan Chitnis, Malaria Parasite Biology and Vaccines, Department of Parasites and Insect Vector, Institute Pasteur, Paris, France** at National Institute of Malaria Research on 21 March 2018
- Attended **Safety Training** at National Institute of Malaria Research on 4th April 2018

Experimental Biology skills

- Isolation, purification and enumeration of microbes from environmental samples

Microbial phenotypic & Biochemical Analysis

- Microbial staining: Simple staining, Negative staining, Gram’s staining, Acid-fast staining, Capsule staining, Spore staining
- Microbial Cultural characterization - Gram characteristic, motility, presence of endospore and capsule, IMViC, TSI, sugar fermentation, nitrate reduction, urease production, oxidase and catalase tests
- Preparation of competent cells, glycerol stock
- Antibiotic susceptibility test and minimal inhibitory concentration detection.
- Estimation of unknown sugar, Bradford and Lowry method (Protein Estimation) proteins concentration using standard curve
- Isolation and enumeration of bacteriophage and animal viruses by plaque formation & chick embryo techniques.
- Determination of bacterial and yeast cell growth kinetics
- Microbial fermentations for the production and estimation of Enzymes, Amino acids, Organic acids, Alcohol, Antibiotic
- Immunological analysis (Antigen-antibody reactions) blood group typing, TLC, DLC, ODD, Dot-ELISA, Immunoelectrophoresis Radial immunodiffusion assay, Haemocytometer.

Molecular Biology Techniques

- Isolation & purification of bacterial genomic DNA and Plasmid from growing culture & natural sample.
- Cloning of Plasmidial gene and expression of protein
- Isolation of Plasmodium DNA, Plasmid
- Production, isolation and characterization of randomly generated mutant
- Transformation of *E. coli* using plasmid DNA.
- Restriction digestion of genomic DNA by endonucleases
- Ligation of Insert into vector
- Primer Designing
- Techniques: PCR- (Gradient, Nested, Reverse transcriptase,colony), Gel Electrophoresis, SDS-Page, Western Blotting

❖ Protein Purification

Instruments Used

- Simple and compound Light Microscope, Inverted Phase Contrast Light Microscope, Micropipettes, Hot Air Oven, Drying Oven, Microwave oven, Autoclave, Incubator, Orbital shaker, BOD Incubator, Refrigerator, -20 Deep freezer, -80 deep freezers. icemaker machine, Deep-fridge, Electronic Analytical Balance, Distilled Water Plant, Ultrapure Water Purification System, Homogeniser, pH Meter Shaking Water Bath, Desiccator Magnetic Stirrer, Vortex Mixer, Sonicator, Laminar Flow Chamber, Bunsen burner, Inoculation loop, Petri dish/agar plate, Spectrophotometer, PCR Thermocycler, Electrophoresis Unit, Refrigerated Centrifuge, UV illuminator, Gel docking assembly, SDS PAGE unit, Western blot unit, Purification columns

TECHNICAL SOFTWARE SKILLS

- **Windows:** Win XP, Vista & Win 7, WIN 10
- **Tools:** MS Office, Star Office, Open Office,
- **Bioinformatic Utility:**
 - Search tools-** Blastn, Blastp, Psiblast, Blastx, tblastx, tblastn, megablast
 - Alignment tools:** DIALIGN, MUSCLE, MAFT, Clustal W, Clustal omega
 - Evolutionary Analysis tools:** MEGA, Emboss, jalview, treeview splittree, Esript
 - Database:** GenBank, SwissProt, EMBL, mgen,uniport, PDB, BRENDA, KEGG Pathway,PlasmoDB

EXTRACURRICULAR ACTIVITIES

- Organize various events in the school such as National Seminar, Teacher's Day, Farewell and Sports Meet.
- Attended Seminar on Personality Development organized in the school.
- Participated in Science Exhibition at school Level
- Participated in college fest as discipline regulatory committee.
- Participated in the Delhi University marathon.
- Participated in sports and member of dramatics society of college.
- Student partner of Intershala student partner program 7.0 at Intershala.
- Member of National Service Scheme 2016
- Student council Member at Central University Haryana session 2017-18
- National skill development corporation level -4 diploma course in Equity dealer 2014